

Exosomes may prevent cardiac attacks, heart failure, and cardiomyopathy

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Abstract- Since the discovery of exosomes, cardiovascular disease therapeutic research has gained interest. Proteins, cytokines, and miRNAs are among the active chemicals present in stem cell-generated exosomes. Exosomes from stem cells include anticardiomyocyte apoptosis, anticardiomyocyte damage, angiogenesis-promoting miRNAs and growth factors. Exosomes can also be used to prevent heart attacks, hypertension, heart failure, and cardiomyopathy. Using exosomes gives several advantages over stem cell transplantation. Exosome therapy is less stressful, reducing the possibility of abnormal differentiation (e.g., stem cells differentiating into bone, fat, or even tumors). Exosomes cause no obvious negative effects, including fever, allergy, or hemolysis. Exosome therapy has no ethical problems. Exosomes have several advantages, but they also have some downsides when employed. Exosomes are produced throughout the body by a number of cells, and the specific function of exosomes from various sources is challenging to identify. Exosome extraction is challenging, and few exosomes are accessible. This results in an unmet need for a standardized and effective extraction procedure. Exosome content is unstable, susceptible to fluctuations. Although stem cell-derived exosomes have several limitations, they have shown promise in cell-free applications in regenerative medicine. Exosomes, a critical component of the paracrine influence of stem cells, may transfer certain miRNAs, mRNAs, and proteins to target cells, increasing cell proliferation, differentiation, survival, and angiogenesis while blocking apoptosis and inflammation. As a result, cell-free exosomes seem to be a promising CVD therapeutic approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

Inducing cardiomyocyte differentiation and proliferation remains challenging despite considerable breakthroughs in the medical treatment of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), such as medication pretreatment, interventional therapy, and surgery. In fact, infarcted and nonfunctional cardiomyocytes' inability to function properly is a serious issue in CVD therapy. As a result, novel treatments for CVDs, such as cell-based therapies, are required.

Cell therapy is currently widely considered as one of the most promising treatments for cardiovascular diseases (1, 2). Several animal studies have demonstrated the therapeutic efficacy of stem cells in CVDs, including mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) (3, 4, 5, embryonic stem cells (ESCs) (4, 5, and induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) (). Clinical studies have shown that some stem cell-based treatments can help people with cardiovascular diseases (6, 7). Despite these promising outcomes, stem cell therapy's downsides, such as tumorigenic potential, immunological rejection, and low survival, remain a severe constraint, prompting more research into other alternatives. Exosomes (stem cell-secreted nanovesicles) have been shown in several studies to have a cardioprotective activity comparable to stem cells (8). Exosomes have been demonstrated to increase angiogenesis, prevent fibrosis, and reduce apoptosis (9, 10). Exosomes are the tiniest extracellular vesicles (EVs), having a phospholipid bilayer ranging in diameter from 30 to 100 nm. Exosomes offer several benefits in clinical applications over stem cells since they do not generate malignancies. Exosomes may also be able to directly touch cardiac tissue in order to carry and transport various active chemicals to recipient cells (11, 12). The mechanism of exosome targeting is currently unknown. As a result, exosomes might be a potential and successful treatment for cardiovascular disease. We present a brief summary of recent discoveries in stem cell-derived exosomes and their prospective involvement in the treatment of CVDs, followed by a discussion of the exosomes' future in the treatment of CVDs.

II. THE ORIGIN, SECRETION, AND COMPOSITION OF EXOSOMES

Most cells in the body can release exosomes, which are small EVs with phospholipid bilayers. These microscopic EVs were initially found in sheep reticulocytes in 1983 and were given the term "exosomes" (13). Exosomes transport and transmit essential signaling molecules, generating a novel system of intercellular information transmission that has an impact on cell physiological status and is linked to the onset and progression of many illnesses (14). Exosomes can be found in blood, tears, urine, saliva, breast milk, and ascites, among other bodily fluids. Regardless of their cell origin, most exosomes exhibit unique surface markers such as CD63, CD81, CD9, TSG101, and HSP27. Exosomes

from different types of cells have diverse interior contents, and so can perform diverse biological tasks. Exosomes have been discovered to transport a wide range of critical biological materials, including lipids, proteins, messenger RNA (mRNA), microRNA (miRNA, miR), and other noncoding RNA. Exosomes contain modest levels of large-molecular-weight RNAs, such as mRNAs and long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs), but they are less stable than miRNAs, which are prone to degradation. Consequently, their stability and detection repeatability are inferior to miRNAs (14,15,16,17).

Exosomes are rich in miRNAs, which can be released by a variety of cells. Exosome-bound miRNAs might be used as key biomarkers for the early identification of a variety of disorders, including cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes, and renal disease (18,19,20). Surprisingly, investigations have revealed that exosome-bound miRNAs play an important regulatory function in CVDs (21,22,23).

Exosomes Derived from Various Stem Cell Types

Exosome research is now centered mostly in the realm of stem cells (7, 24). The positive benefits of stem cell repair of cardiac tissue are thought to be mediated through a paracrine pathway (7, 25, 26). Exosomes, as bioactive paracrine substances produced by stem cells, have the ability to improve heart function after damage by influencing angiogenesis, cytoprotection, fibrosis, contractility, and regeneration for new cell production (11, 27). Exosomes, as a typical representative paracrine component of stem cells, have recently been revealed to be critical for regulating cell signal transmission and disease biological activity (7, 28).

Exosomes Derived from ESCs ESCs are totipotent cells that may develop into nearly any type of adult tissue cell. This has been proven in immature cardiomyocytes, which express myocyte-specific structural proteins as well as other muscle-specific genes (29, 30). However, ethical considerations and immunologic rejection prevent these cells from being used in clinical trials. Human ESCs have been shown to release 50–100 nm vesicles for the first time. Purified exosomes were found to minimize the extent of myocardial infarction in rats using an I/R-damaged isolated Langendorff model (4). Exosomes produced from ESCs have been shown to cause cardiac hyperplasia. Many mRNAs, proteins, and particular miRNAs are abundant in exosomes generated from ESCs. In oxidative stress, they can increase cell proliferation, survival, and angiogenesis by transferring their exosomal contents to recipient cells (31). Recent research suggests that ESC-derived exosomes stimulate cardiomyocyte proliferation and cardiovascular development, increasing heart repair and improving cardiac function following acute ischemia. Furthermore, anticardiomyocyte apoptosis and antimyocardial fibrosis capabilities have been discovered in these exosomes (4).

III. EXOSOMES ARE PRODUCED BY IPSCS.

IPSCs, like ESCs, can multiply and differentiate, and with the right induction circumstances, they can differentiate into any type of cell. Exosomes generated from iPSCs and ESCs, as well as their contents, have recently been discovered to stimulate heart repair and improve cardiac function. Exosomes produced from iPSCs have been demonstrated in studies to reduce myocardial fibrosis (32), preserve wounded myocardium (33), and reduce limb ischemia by boosting cardiovascular production (34, 35).

Furthermore, encouraging data demonstrates that exosomes produced from iPSCs can differentiate cardiac-derived MSCs into cardiac and endothelial cells (33) while still maintaining iPSC pluripotency (36). Exosomes produced from iPSCs can decrease apoptosis in H9C2 cells under hydrogen peroxide-induced oxidative stress by inhibiting caspase 3/7 activation. These findings suggest that exosomes produced from iPSCs might be very useful in the treatment of CVDs.

IV. EXOSOMES DERIVED FROM MSCS ARE A KIND OF EXOSOME THAT IS PRODUCED BY MSCS.

Adult pluripotent cells (MSCs) can be found in a variety of adult tissues, although bone marrow tissue has the highest concentration. MSCs are known to have a high plasticity of differentiation and can develop into a variety of cells *in vitro* and *in vivo*, including osteoblasts, chondrocytes, adipocytes, and cardiomyocytes. MSCs are the most common stem cells employed in CVD clinical studies. MSC-derived exosomes are 40–100 nm diameter homogeneous membrane vesicles released by MSCs in normal or pathological settings (3, 37). Exosomes generated from MSCs primarily regulate mRNA, miRNA, and protein levels, which subsequently influence target cell activity via a variety of regulatory mechanisms (38). MSC-derived exosomes include a vast variety of biologically active molecules that alter target cell activity by transferring biologically active substances to target cells via membrane fusion or endocytosis (39). MSC-derived exosomes have been linked to acute myocardial infarction (AMI), hypertension, heart failure (HF), and cardiomyopathy in the cardiovascular sector (40). In a pig myocardial ischemia-reperfusion paradigm, MSC-derived exosomes were demonstrated to minimize myocardial infarction areas and enhance heart function. Implantation of human MSC-derived exosomes into mice has been demonstrated in other research to greatly increase cardiomyocyte regeneration and enhance cardiac function (41, 42). Furthermore, earlier research has proven the involvement of exosomes in angiogenesis and creation, which is predominantly accomplished through their modulation of extracellular matrix metalloproteinase inducers (43).

The Importance of Exosomes in the Diagnosis and Treatment of Cardiovascular Disease

Exosomes in the Diagnosis of Cardiovascular Diseases Biomarkers with Exosomes

Exosome secretion is strongly linked to a cell's physiological and pathological circumstances. Exosome content varies depending on the physiological condition of the cells. Exosome content can be employed as a biomarker to assess normal biological and pathological processes, as well as therapeutic treatments (44). Exosomes have been demonstrated to be important communicators of heart healing in a variety of studies linked to myocardial infarction, and monitoring these exosomes can be employed as diagnostic and prognostic markers (45, 46). As a result, exosomes may play a key role in the future as biomarkers for CVDs. Exosomes include miRNAs, which are not only endogenous genetic regulators but also biomarkers that govern intercellular communication (47, 48).

Exosomes generated from cardiomyocytes contain up to 1520 different kinds of miRNAs (49). Recent research suggests that plasma levels of exosome-associated miRNAs might be used as novel biomarkers for myocardial infarction diagnosis. MiRNAs associated with exosomes, such as miR-1, miR-208b, miR-133a/b, and miR-499, are prevalent in cardiac tissue (50). MiR-208b and miR-499, for example, have been shown to be considerably elevated in the plasma of AMI patients (51). Other research has suggested that miR-208a might be a marker for myocardial infarction in its early stages (19). Additional research has demonstrated that myocardial-specific miRNAs play a substantial role in the pathophysiology of CVDs, and that miRNA expression is more easily detectable in patients' blood-derived exosomes as the illness progresses (52). In certain disease situations, distinct kinds of miRNAs are enriched. Exosomes isolated from urine and blood samples from individuals with AMI had higher levels of cardiac-specific miR-1 and miR-208. In addition, in the early stages of HF following AMI, the expression of small RNAs linked with p53 genes (miR-192, miR-194, and miR-34a) was considerably enhanced (53). Cardiomyocytes actively produce miR-194 and miR-34a in the peripheral circulation, which is mostly encased in exosomes. As a result, miRNAs in circulation are strongly linked to left ventricular diastolic function and might be used as biomarkers (54). The function of miRNAs in exosomes as diagnostic biomarkers for illnesses like lung cancer and ovarian cancer has lately received a lot of attention (55, 56). MiR-21 and miR-146a expression in exosomes is elevated in cervical cancer, and these miRNAs are being investigated as possible biomarkers for cervical cancer detection (57). Exosomes also include DNA, mRNA, other noncoding RNAs and proteins such as heat shock protein (Hsp) 70 and Hsp90, growth factors, vascular cell adhesion factor 1 (VCAF1), and Y chromosome sex-determining region genes, in addition to miRNA. Some of them, such as early HF and atherosclerosis, can be employed as biomarkers for CVDs (58). The technology for detecting miRNAs is currently mature, the detection difficulty is minimal, and the findings are consistent and trustworthy. As a result, myocardial-specific miRNAs in exosomes might be useful biomarkers for detecting CVDs in the clinic (59, 60).

Exosomes in the Prevention and Treatment of Cardiovascular Disease

Stem cell therapy has emerged as a possible therapeutic option for cardiovascular disease. However, poor implantation, survival, and differentiation potential after transplantation, as well as ethical problems, immunological incompatibility, and teratoma development, are all serious barriers to cell treatment. Furthermore, in clinical therapy, stem cell transplantation may create an electric signal, which might be a source of arrhythmia. Fortunately, exosome-based treatment created from stem cells might be a novel approach that avoids the drawbacks of cell treatment (61). Exosomes generated from ESCs, iPSCs, and MSCs have been shown to induce cardiomyocyte proliferation, promote angiogenesis, reduce apoptosis, and inhibit fibrosis, suggesting that they might be employed for cardiac protection and therapy (28, 62).

Myocardial Infarction and Exosomes

Myocardial infarction is defined as an acute or chronic obstruction of the coronary arteries that results in cardiomyocyte apoptosis and destruction (45). AMI is a severe form of coronary heart disease in which normal blood pumping capacity is lost as a result of coronary blockage, blood flow stoppage, and partial necrosis of some myocardium owing to severe and prolonged ischemia (63, 64). Myocardial infarction is an irreparable damage that is the major cause of mortality in those who have cardiovascular disease. Thrombolysis, percutaneous coronary artery interventional therapy, and coronary artery bypass graft are some of the current AMI treatments that can alleviate symptoms of myocardial ischemia and HF and recanalize blocked vessels (65). However, because of cardiomyocytes' lack of proliferative capability, these approaches can not be used to replace necrotic cardiomyocytes. The necrotic or nonfunctioning myocardium has no method of recovering and functioning properly, which has become a serious concern in the treatment of cardiac problems. Stem cell transplantation has recently been shown to enhance heart function via a paracrine impact (66, 67). Many paracrine factors produced by stem cells directly mend regenerated cardiac tissue, allowing them to enable cell-free therapy in the future. Exosomes have been widely researched for the therapy of CVDs as a paracrine aggregation of stem cells (68). Exosomes produced from stem cells have been demonstrated to improve heart function by suppressing cardiomyocyte apoptosis, suppressing the inflammatory response to protect cardiomyocytes, suppressing myocardial remodeling, increasing angiogenesis, and minimizing ischemia-reperfusion damage, among other things.

V. EFFECTS OF ANTIAPOPTOSIS

Coronary artery stenosis and obstruction, as well as inadequate myocardial blood flow, cause apoptosis, necrosis, and cell death in myocardial cells, resulting in myocardial infarction. Repairing the infarcted myocardium in the clinic is tough due to the difficulty of regenerating cardiomyocytes. With the introduction of stem cell treatment, a therapeutic option for cardiomyocyte repair has been available. The purpose of stem cells is to prevent anticardiomyocyte apoptosis via a paracrine mechanism rather than to directly develop into cardiomyocytes (26, 69). MiR-22 in ESC-derived exosomes was discovered to diminish methylation of CpG binding protein-2 and decrease cardiomyocyte apoptosis following myocardial infarction (66). Furthermore, by delivering exosome content to receptor cells in a condition of oxidative stress, ESC-derived exosomes can enhance cardiomyocyte proliferation, survival, and cardiovascular production (4). Under hydrogen peroxide-induced

oxidative stress, iPSC-derived exosomes have been demonstrated to prevent apoptosis in H9C2 cardiomyocytes by reducing caspase 3/7 activation (34). Recent research has found that bone marrow MSCs prevent ischemia cardiomyocyte damage by targeting exosomal miR-22 transfer to diminish CpG binding protein-2 methylation and cardiomyocyte death (70). By suppressing the expression of P53 and downregulating the expression of the apoptosis-inducing protein Bcl-2b, MiR-221 in exosomes mediates the antiapoptotic impact of bone marrow MSCs (71).

MSC-conditioned media was utilized to treat hypoxic and serum-free H9C2 cells in earlier cell investigations. The findings also revealed that MSC-conditioned media may trigger hypoxia-induced apoptosis in H9C2 cells, with exosomes present in the conditioned medium (72). In conclusion, exosomes are implicated in the anticardiomyocyte apoptotic pathway (73).

Effects on Inflammation

Exosomes from dendritic cells and tumor cells are well recognized for their role in reducing inflammatory response and are being evaluated as possible treatments for certain disorders. Exosome treatment has been shown to minimize systemic inflammation following myocardial I/R in mice. Similarly, other investigations have shown that MSC-derived exosomes from bone marrow have comparable benefits in the treatment of CVDs, such as MSC-derived exosomes suppressing inflammation and reducing pulmonary hypertension (74). Neutrophil and macrophage infiltration were utilized to assess the inflammatory response following an AMI in prior research. When mice were given MSC-derived exosomes, the amount of neutrophils and macrophages in their venous blood was much lower than when they were given normal saline (71). Simultaneously, the benefits of MSC-derived exosomes on infarct size reduction and cardiac function improvement were demonstrated. Exosomes produced from MSCs were also reported to activate M2 macrophages and reduce the development of inflammatory responses following AMI (75). Furthermore, exosomes produced from ESC or iPSC protect against CVDs by suppressing the local immunological and inflammatory response (4, 31, 76, 77, 78). Exosomes produced by stem cells protect the myocardium by decreasing the inflammatory response in CVDs, according to this research.

Anticardiac Remodeling is a term used to describe a process in which the

Myocardial remodeling is a compensatory mechanism for a variety of CVDs, such as ventricular hypertrophy and myocardial fibrosis, the most prevalent form of heart failure, which often goes untreated. In animal investigations, indices of left ventricular size, myocardial fibrosis, and cardiomyocyte apoptosis are frequently used to describe myocardial remodeling (79, 80). After myocardial remodeling, ESC-derived exosomes have been demonstrated to increase neovascularization, decrease fibrosis, and boost the survival of c-kit+ cardiac progenitor cells (CPCs) (4). Similarly, recent research has found that exosomes formed from iPSCs and their contents protect wounded myocardium, and that these effects are favorable for wound healing and fibrosis reduction following cardiac remodeling (81). Exosomes generated from bone marrow MSCs have also been demonstrated to improve cardiomyocyte viability by activating prosurvival signals, lowering oxidative stress, and inhibiting unfavorable remodeling during cardiac ischemia-reperfusion damage (82). MSCs were shown to stimulate endogenous cardiac repair and enhance myocardial remodeling mostly through paracrine pathways in a clinical investigation of employing MSCs to treat HF (25, 83). Although the influence of stem cell-derived exosomes on cardiac remodeling is well understood, the exact mechanism is unknown and needs to be validated by more fundamental research.

Angiogenesis

Angiogenesis is the process of generating new blood vessels from existing endothelial cells, and it is crucial for cardiac healing after a heart attack. The establishment of diverse pathogenic microenvironments causes necrosis and apoptosis in cardiomyocytes. The available pharmacological, surgical, and interventional therapy options are currently restricted. Exosomes produced from stem cells have been proven in studies to induce angiogenesis and may be a potential therapeutic strategy. Many of these paracrine substances from stem cells have been shown to have favorable effects on the heart, such as neovascularization, ventricular wall thinning prevention, and enhanced angiogenesis. Exosomes produced from stem cells can be used to test the potential of human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) to stimulate tube formation and angiogenesis in the heart. Furthermore, encouraging data shows that exosomes produced from iPSCs might help promote angiogenesis (84, 85). Exosomes produced from iPSCs have also been found in the region of myocardial infarction, suggesting that they may play a role in angiogenesis (85). Furthermore, while some studies have demonstrated that MSC-derived exosomes might increase angiogenic activity, the precise therapeutic mechanism of MSC-derived exosomes in ischemic hearts is unknown (86). In a rat model of myocardial infarction, human bone marrow MSC-derived EVs were found to stimulate angiogenesis (87). According to this research, EVs include some of the key bioactive elements that protect against myocardial infarction and promote angiogenesis. Another set of research (88) established the relevance of MSC-derived exosomes in stimulating vessel development and angiogenesis, with the modulation of extracellular matrix metalloproteinase inducers as the primary mechanism. Angiogenesis has emerged as a key research focus for stem cell-derived exosomes in the treatment of CVDs.

Myocardial Ischemia-Reperfusion Injury and Exosomes

Due to oxygen free radical generation, calcium overload, and other factors, restoration of blood flow after a myocardial infarction may produce myocardial cell metabolic instability and cardiac dysfunction, exacerbating myocardial tissue damage (88). In clinical therapy, repetitive and temporary myocardial ischemic preconditioning is commonly employed to enhance myocardial stress generation and endogenous protective

chemical release to reduce damage during ischemia-reperfusion (89, 90). In myocardial infarction, myocardial ischemic preconditioning can improve myocardial tolerance to long-term ischemia and diminish myocardial damage caused by long-term ischemia and reperfusion (91). Exosomes formed from stem cells have been found to reduce cardiac damage induced by ischemia-reperfusion and to improve the protective impact of exosomes on the myocardium in simulated hypoxia pretreatment stem cells (81). In both pig and mouse models of myocardial ischemia/reperfusion (MI/R) damage, media conditioned by human embryonic stem cell (ESC)-derived MSCs (hESC-MSCs) dramatically decreased infarct size (92). In a pig cardiac ischemia and reperfusion model, intravenous and intracoronary therapy with MSC-derived conditioned medium (MSC-CM) resulted in a considerable decrease in infarct size (91, 93).

Furthermore, isolated exosomes from MSC-CM were found to have cardioprotective properties in a mouse MI damage model (39, 70). Injection of cardiac progenitor exosomes prepared with hypoxia improved cardiac function and reduced myocardial fibrosis in another investigation (89). Further research has discovered that inhibiting miRNA and RNA-induced gene silencing complexes can reverse cardiac progenitor exosomes' protective impact on the myocardium. As a result, miRNA transfer and subsequent gene silencing are crucial ways in which exosomes protect cells. Myocardial ischemia preconditioning produces exosomes that can effectively minimize apoptosis and myocardial remodeling induced by myocardial infarction, as well as serve a protective function in the myocardium. The transfer of miR-22 by exosomes is primarily responsible for this mechanism (70-274).

Exosome Advantages and Disadvantages

Since the discovery of exosomes, research on the therapy of cardiovascular diseases has gotten a lot of interest. Proteins, cytokines, and miRNAs are among the physiologically active compounds found in exosomes generated from stem cells. Exosomes generated from stem cells include antiscardiomycocyte apoptosis, antiscardiomycocyte damage, angiogenesis-promoting, and anti-inflammatory miRNAs and growth factors. Exosomes can also be employed to prevent and cure heart attacks, hypertension, heart failure, and cardiomyopathy (94). The use of exosomes provides a number of benefits for stem cell transplantation. (i) Exosome treatment is less stressful, and the risk of aberrant differentiation is reduced (e.g., stem cells differentiating into bone, fat, or even tumors). (ii) Exosomes do not cause any noticeable side effects, such as fever, allergies, or hemolysis. (iii) Exosome treatment raises no ethical concerns. Exosomes offer a number of advantages, but they also have a number of drawbacks when used. (i) Exosomes are secreted by a variety of cells throughout the body, and it is hard to pinpoint the precise function of exosomes from diverse sources. (ii) Exosome extraction is difficult, and the number of exosomes available is restricted. As a result, there is an unmet demand for a standardized and effective extraction process. (iii) Extraordinary content is unstable and changeable. Although stem cell-derived exosomes have a few limitations, they have shown considerable promise in cell-free applications in regenerative medicine.

VI. CONCLUSION

Exosomes, which are a key component of stem cells' paracrine impact, may deliver particular miRNAs, mRNAs, and proteins to target cells, promoting cell proliferation, differentiation, survival, and angiogenesis while inhibiting apoptosis and inflammation. As a result, cell-free exosomes appear to be a viable CVD treatment option.

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